

UNIT COST AND COST-EFFECTIVENESS ANALYSIS: A CASE STUDY OF AN INDUSTRIAL TRAINING INSTITUTE (ITI) IN MANIPUR

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Abstract

The current article aimed at finding out the unit cost per student and cost-effectiveness. It was a case study of most sought after courses, such as Mechanic, Electrician, and Motor Mechanic under the National Council for Vocational Training (NCVT) in an Industrial Training Institute (ITI) located at Takyelpat, Imphal West District, Manipur. The total enrolment (i.e., cohort) for Mechanic and Electrician was 20 each, while for Motor Mechanic, it was 22 students. The expenditure incurred on the salaries of the teachers during two years' period of the courses 2014-2016 was the basis of cost calculation. The results indicated wastage in all the three courses due to dropout and/or stagnation at varying rates. For Mechanic Course, the effective unit cost was estimated at Rs.75,337 as against the 'normal' unit cost of Rs.61,639 with a wastage rate of 55 per cent; for Electrician, the effective unit cost was Rs.75,932 instead of Rs.49,356 with 35 per cent wastage; and for Motor Mechanic, the effective unit cost was worked out to be Rs.97,841 in lieu of Rs.55,909 with a wastage of 64 per cent. Thus, out of a total salary costs of Rs.34,49,910 during 2014-16, Rs.18,06,248 had been lost owing to dropout (18%) and stagnation (34%) with a total wastage of 52 per cent. The generalizability of the findings of the study would merit further investigation. However, it would give us an insight into the situations on the ground of the present institute in particular and other similar institutes in general. Certain measures for improvement had been suggested.

Keywords: Cost, unit cost, effective cost, cohort, dropout, stagnation, wastage, 'normal cost', polytechnic, course, per student.

Introduction

In the present study, an attempt was made to work out the 'normal' unit cost per student and the cost-effectiveness or internal efficiency of the costs. In this context, we shall highlight here about cost-effectiveness analysis and cost-benefit analysis. Cost-effectiveness analysis in education is used to address only those questions that relate to the 'internal efficiency' of resources invested, while the cost-benefit analysis examines the 'external efficiency' of investments made. Though both constitute economic evaluations, the outputs of the former are measured in terms of the physical output, such as levels of achievements, promotion or transition to the next level of education, etc., while the outputs

of the latter are measured in monetary terms, such as labour market rewards for education. The “*effective unit cost of education relates to cost-effectiveness analysis*” (Tilak, 1997, p. 25). “*The effective costs of education are calculated per unit of output, i.e., per successful student. The difference between effective costs and ‘normal’ cost of education reveals the efficiency of the given level of the educational system. The larger the difference, the higher the inefficiency, and vice-versa*” (Ibid.).

Study on the economics of education appeared to be still a very new area of interest, though its importance was emphasized some fifty years ago. It was for the first time in India that the unit cost per student was studied in twelve Indian Universities during 1964-66 on the recommendations of the Indian Education Commission 1964-66 known as the Kothari Commission. Following the recommendations of the Commission, a seminar on **Measurement of Cost Productivity and Efficiency of Education** was organized by the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) at Jaipur from 27 November to 2 December 1967. This seminar was the first of its kind in India following the recommendations of the Kothari Commission 1964-66 for the study of unit costs of education.

After the seminar, a book entitled **Measurement of Cost Productivity and Efficiency of Education** (the topic of the seminar itself) edited by Pandit (1969) was published. The book consists of 32 different papers divided into V sections as: Section I: Methodology for Costing of Education and Empirical Studies; Section II: Measurement of Efficiency of Education; Section III: Economic Criteria for Investment in Education; Section IV: Productivity of Education and Policy Issues; and Section V: Review of Literature and Problems in Measurement of Cost-Benefit of Education.

Here, some of the studies relevant to the present study are reviewed as under:

Pandit (1969) in his paper on ‘A Study in Unit Costs at the School Stage in India: A Design of the Research Project’ spelt out that the unit cost can be studied in relation to the ‘internal and external efficiency’ of school stage educational system, among others. He classified ‘efficiency’ into ‘internal’ and ‘external’. Internal efficiency is the study of the problems relating to wastage and stagnation, thereby determining the qualitative aspects of the internal working of the school system. The external efficiency of the system indicates coordination between school stage educational sector and economic aspects. In terms of quantity, it attempts to measure how far the system produces the required numbers of pupils needed for the remaining sectors. The qualitative aspect tries to show whether the educational sector is producing the types of output needed according to the present and future needs of the economy. Pandit also suggested that the quality of output can be judged on the basis of the internal and external efficiency of the educational system.

Adhvaryu (1969) also classified the economic efficiency criterion into: “*internal efficiency of the educational system and its external efficiency. Internal efficiency refers to the simple intake and out-turn of pupils and students. It deals with possible waste in the educational system owing to drop-outs and stagnation in the system of various levels. He suggested that per student cost become so important in the theory of investment in education from the point of view of internal efficiency*” (p.142). The external efficiency of the system depends on how efficiently it meets the needed manpower by the economy both in terms of quantity and quality. The quantitative external efficiency rests on how efficiently the system is able to supply the quantitative needs for manpower, such as engineers, doctors, technicians, economists, etc. The qualitative external efficiency would deal with the problem whether the manpower released by the educational system satisfies the specific requirements of the jobs. In this context, Adhvaryu gave an example from the experience in India and that in India there is a general tendency that the numbers of applications are in excess of the number of vacancies advertised. However, from amongst the applicants called for interview, it becomes difficult to secure suitable

candidates in the strength adequate enough to fill the vacancies. It suggested that the external qualitative efficiency is low.

Some studies on the internal and external efficiency of education with reference to the cost-effectiveness and cost-benefit analysis have been reviewed above. Furthermore, we shall examine briefly the importance of unit cost study. As stated above, it was for the first time in India that the Kothari Commission 1964-66 recommended to study the unit cost being a comparatively new field, where not much systematic work has been done so far in India (*see* The Report, Vol. IV, pp. 928-933, Supplementary Note IV).

About the need of unit cost study, Sharma (1969) pointed out:

“The unit costs are needed:

- i. For working out financial allocations and costing of educational programmes;*
- ii. For studying the level of efficiency at which the educational plant is run;*
- iii. To ensure optimum utilization and to improve the efficiency of resources invested in education through their analysis and consideration of various alternative combinations of their components; and*
- iv. To measure the costs of inputs in the education industry in determining the returns to education and productivity of the process”* (pp. 27-28).

Datt (1969) suggested two ways about the importance of the study of unit costs:

“It helps us to know the cost of creation of seats in educational institutions, and, secondly, it also enables us to know the cost of operation of the seats created...” (p.92).

About the importance of the quality of student input, Basu et al. (1974) studied economics of education in some West Bengal colleges and reported that the only variable which has important and significant effect on output is the student input and that some colleges can produce better output not because they have better environment but because they have better input. It indicated that input student quality is very important for better output.

Rationale of the Study

The importance of the study of unit costs and cost-effectiveness had been highlighted above. Furthermore, such a study would be helpful in ascertaining the benefit/profit or loss of the costs, especially in the internal efficiency of investments in education. It would also help us in institutional planning, estimating requirement of resources for education, monitoring and improvement of utilization of resources, among others. The current study would also enable the educational planners and policy makers to ascertain the extent of profit or loss for the investment made in such expensive technical institute, thereby helping provide feedback on the costs.

Objectives

- 1) To find out the unit cost per student of three courses – Mechanic, Electrician, and Motor Mechanic – on the salary expenditure of the teachers in an Industrial Training Institute (ITI) during 2014-2016.
- 2) To work out the effective unit cost per student in three courses – Mechanic, Electrician, and Motor Mechanic, 2 years in each course under the National Council for Vocational Training (NCVT) in the Industrial Training Institute (ITI).
- 3) To suggest certain appropriate measures for improvement.

Methods

The case study approach was adopted in the investigation, in which an Industrial Training Institute located at Takyelpat, Imphal West District, Manipur, was selected as a sample through the purposive sampling. This sample was selected with a view to ascertaining the situations on the ground of the oldest institute established in 1959 in Manipur. Moreover, the three courses under study were the most sought after ones from among the 23 trades currently operating in this institute.

Sources of Data

The study was mainly analytical in nature, in which the sources of data were from the official records maintained by the institute consisting of the following:

- Enrolment from August 2014 to August 2016 in Mechanic, Electrician, and Motor Mechanic.
- Salary expenditure on teachers of the three courses for the period August 2014 to August 2016.
- Number of students appeared in the examinations – passed or failed.
- Dropout records.

The data were analysed using percentage.

Operational Definitions

- **Unit cost** refers to the “*cost per student enrolled, i.e., ‘normal’ unit cost of education = Total costs/Enrolment*” (Tilak, 1997, p.15).
- **Effective unit cost** refers to the “*cost per successful student = Total costs/No. of pass-outs*” (Ibid.). In other words, it is the total unit cost found after distributing equally the total amount lost due to wastage to each successful student over and above their ‘normal’ unit cost.
- **Cost-effectiveness** and **internal efficiency** were used synonymously and interchangeably. It refers to the ability of the system to produce the maximum number of outputs with the minimum dropout and stagnation.
- **Cost** refers to the recurring salary costs of teachers from August 2014 to August 2016.
- **Stagnation** refers to the student (s) staying in the same class for more than the prescribed period.

Total wastage had been taken to include both ‘dropout’ and ‘stagnation’.

- **Cohort** refers to the group of students enrolled in a particular course.
- **Calculation of Input and Output**

The number of students admitted in the year 2014-15 (i.e., cohort) was the input of the study, while the number passed out in 2015-16 was the output. In this process, they were studied by tracing their progress throughout the 2 years’ period and wastage due to dropout and stagnation was also examined.

Assumption

- “If the ITI was able to produce the maximum output, given the cost, it can be said to be operating very efficiently.”

Or

- “If the effective unit cost was higher than that of the normal unit cost, it can be said that the institute was operating very inefficiently.”

Results and Discussion

Objective 1: To find out the unit cost per student of three courses – Mechanic, Electrician, and Motor Mechanic – on the salary expenditure of the teachers in an Industrial Training Institute (ITI) during 2014-2016.

Table-1 Course-wise cohort, dropped out, appeared, stagnated, passed out, and wastage due to dropout & stagnation

Courses	Cohort	Dropped out	Appeared	Stagnated	Passed out	Wastage
Mechanic	20	9 (45)	11 (55)	2 (10)	9 (45)	11 (55)
Electrician	20	0 (00)	20 (100)	7 (35)	13 (65)	7 (35)
Motor Mechanic	22	2 (9)	20 (91)	12 (55)	8 (36)	14 (64)
Total:	62	11 (18)	51 (82)	21 (34)	30 (48)	32 (52)

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentage of that particular row)

The results indicated that the highest dropout rate was found in Mechanic with 45 per cent, followed by Motor Mechanic with 9 per cent, but no dropout case in Electrician.

About stagnation, the highest was recorded in Motor Mechanic with 55 per cent, Electrician 35 per cent, and Mechanic 36 per cent.

The total wastage due to dropout and stagnation in case of Mechanic and Motor Mechanic was 55 and 64 per cent respectively, while 35 per cent wastage was recorded in Electrician owing to stagnation. Among the three courses, Electrician was in a better position than Mechanic and Motor Mechanic. The overall wastage was estimated at 52 per cent with dropout 18 per cent and stagnation 34 per cent.

Objective 2: To work out the effective unit cost per student in three courses – Mechanic, Electrician, and Motor Mechanic, 2 years in each course under the National Council for Vocational Training (NCVT) in the Industrial Training Institute (ITI).

Table-2 Course-wise Cohort, Unit of Wastage due to dropout and stagnation, Gross salary costs, Normal unit costs based on cohort, Excess costs per unit due to wastage, Effective unit costs, and Total amount of wastage during 2014-2016 (in Rs.)

Courses and Cohort	Unit of Wastage due to dropout & Stagnation	Gross Salary Costs	Normal Unit Costs based on Cohort (Average)	Excess Costs Per Unit due to Wastage (Average)	Effective Unit Costs=Normal Unit Costs+Excess Cost (Average)	Total Amount of Wastage based on Unit of Wastage x Normal Unit Costs (Average)
Mechanic 20 (100)	11 (55)	12,32,782 (100)	61,639	13,698	75,337	6,78,030 (55)
Electrician 20 (100)	7 (35)	9,87,128 (100)	49,356	26,576	75,932	3,45,492 (35)

Motor Mechanic 22 (100)	14 (64)	12,30,000 (100)	55,909	41,932	97,841	7,82,726 (64)
62 (100)	32 (52)	34,49,910 (100)	55,635	27,402	83,037	18,06,248 (52)

(Figures in the parentheses indicate percentage of that particular row)

N.B. Totals do not tally due to rounding.

The results indicated that, for Mechanic Course, the total amount lost due to wastage of 11 students out of a cohort of 20 students was worked out to be Rs. 6,78,030 (55%), in which the Institute had to spend an excess costs of Rs. 13,698 per student who had completed the course over and above their normal unit cost of Rs. 61,639 with an effective unit cost of Rs. 75,337 per student.

For Electrician, the normal unit cost was estimated at Rs.49,356, but with an additional costs of Rs.26,576 per student, the effective unit cost became Rs.75,932 per student, thereby leading to a total wastage of Rs. 3,45,492 (35%) resulting from a wastage of 7 students @ Rs.49,356 normal unit cost per student.

In case of Motor Mechanic, the effective unit cost was found to be Rs.97,841 with the addition of Rs. 41,932 to the normal unit cost of Rs. 55,909. The total amount lost due to the wastage of 14 out of 22 students was estimated at Rs. 7,82,726 (64%).

The results revealed that the highest wastage rate was found in case of Motor Mechanic with 64 per cent, followed by Mechanic with 55 per cent, and then Electrician with 35 per cent. If there happened to be no wastage, Mechanic Course could have saved Rs.5,54,752 (45%). Electrician Rs. 6,41,636 (65%), and Motor Mechanic Rs.4,47,274 (36%) with a total of Rs.16,43,662 (48%) for these three courses, but failed owing to wastage 32 students out of 62 cohort, as a result, altogether Rs.18,06,248 (52%) had been wasted during the two years course of the three trades.

Findings

- The highest wastage of Rs.7,82,726 (64%) was noted in Motor Mechanic Course, as the effective unit cost was estimated at Rs.97,841 with an additional expenditure of Rs.41,932 per successful student over and above their normal unit cost of Rs.55,909.
- Mechanic Course occupied the second highest wastage of Rs.6,78,030 (55%), in which the effective unit cost was worked out to be Rs.75,337 with the addition of Rs.13,698 to the normal unit cost of Rs.61,639.
- The least wastage of Rs.3,45,492 (35%) was noted in Electrician Course with an effective unit cost of Rs.75,932 per successful student as against the normal unit cost of Rs.49,356 plus an additional amount of Rs.26,576 per unit.
- The overall wastage was 52 per cent resulting from dropout 18 per cent and stagnation 34 per cent.

Conclusion

It was evident from the findings of the study that all the three courses were not operating efficiently at all. Though the generalizability of the results to other similar institute would merit further investigation, it would have been no exception only to the three courses of the Institute. On the other

hand, if the findings emerging from the current study of only three courses of two years could be generalized to the present institute and other similar institutes having different courses/trades, then the extent of wastage would have been an untold one. Realizing the gravity of the situation, it was high time to explore the reasons behind it with a strong determination to resolve the 'issue' at the earliest. "The earliest the better".

As mentioned just above, the results indicated 'huge' wastage of 52 per cent owing to dropout and stagnation. One of the basic reasons for such a state of affairs might be what is termed as lack of "cost consciousness" among the Governments (Sharma, 1980, p.89). If so, whatever amount invested in education needed to be utilized precisely, economically, and effectively.

The findings emerging from such a limited analysis may serve as a real eye-opener for educational planners and policy makers in bringing about cost consciousness. As technical education is more expensive than the general education, it was absolutely imperative to investigate how and why there was such a large amount of wastage and do the needful accordingly. In case of failure to do so, a wastage after a wastage would eventually lead to massive wastage of resources in terms of time, efforts, money, and human.

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